

An Analysis of the State of Inclusive and Special Basic Schools in Nigeria: Insights from the Universal Basic Education Commission's 2022 Data

Ashara, Ozioma Chinasa
Department of Educational Foundations
University of Lagos, Nigeria
ozidichi@gmail.com

Abstract

This study analysed the state of inclusive and special education at the basic level, leveraging available comprehensive data from the Universal Basic Education Commission's (UBEC) 2022 report. UBEC's data is synthesised on school distribution, pupil enrolment, and teacher availability across different regions and educational levels. The findings reveal substantial disparities between inclusive and special schools, with inclusive schools being far more numerous, particularly at the primary level. Significant regional differences exist, with the North West having the highest number of both inclusive and special schools. Pupil enrolment is notably higher in inclusive schools, especially at the primary level. The study identifies gifted students as the largest category of special needs students in inclusive schools. However, it also highlights critical shortages in special education teachers and alarming student-teacher ratios in some regions, particularly in the North East and North West. The paper concludes that while there is a strong drive towards inclusive education in Nigeria, there remains a crucial need for specialised support for students with severe or specific needs. Key recommendations include increased investment in special schools, balanced regional development, enhanced teacher training, and policies to incentivise teachers to work in underserved areas.

Keywords: Universal Basic Education Commission, inclusive school, special schools; Early Childhood Care Development and Education; Gifted students

Introduction

Education for special and inclusive schools has long faced numerous challenges, including inadequate resources, insufficiently trained teachers, and a lack of specialised support for students with diverse needs (Eleweke and Rodda 2002; Angwaomaodoko, 2023). These issues have often resulted in disparities in educational access and quality, particularly for students requiring special education services. Inclusive education, which aims to integrate students with special needs into mainstream schools, has been promoted to foster social integration and equal opportunities among students in Nigeria (UNESCO, 2020). However, the implementation of inclusive education has been hampered by gaps in policy, funding, and infrastructure, leaving many students without the necessary support to thrive.

For many years, there has been a significant gap in addressing the core issues of inclusive education in Nigeria. The lack of comprehensive data on the number and types of schools, the condition of these schools, the enrolment of special needs students, and the number of qualified teachers among other key issues have made it difficult to develop effective policies and allocate resources appropriately. This gap has hindered efforts to improve the educational outcomes for students with special needs and to ensure that all students have access to quality education. Recently, the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) has begun to compile and publish comprehensive data on various aspects of basic education in Nigeria. These data are extensive and cover the public and private educational sector at the State and national levels. The data include a wide range of statistics on the number, types, and status of schools, the condition of these schools, the population of pupils/learners (including special needs learners), educational resources, facilities, and personnel at three basic levels, namely the Early Childhood Care Development and Education (ECCDE), primary and Junior Secondary School (JSS) levels. While UBEC has begun collecting more extensive data on inclusive and special schools (<https://ubec.gov.ng/data/>), this information remains underutilised by stakeholders in the special education sector. This paper synthesised and interpreted this data to inform decision-making and policy development. The availability of this data is a significant step for the educational sector, as it provides a detailed understanding of the current state of education and highlights areas that require attention and improvement.

Therefore, the objective of this paper is to analyse the data provided in UBEC's 2022 Digest of Public and Private Schools to gain insights into the state of gifted and special education in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to: 1) Examine the number and types of inclusive and special basic schools across Nigeria, 2) analyse pupil enrolment patterns in inclusive and special schools, including regional differences and enrolment by special need type, 3) assess the population of gifted and talented pupils in inclusive schools, and 4) evaluate the availability and distribution of teachers in special needs schools, including regional disparities and student-teacher ratios. By addressing these specific objectives, the paper seeks to identify key trends, challenges, and opportunities for improvement, providing actionable recommendations to inform policymakers and stakeholders.

Methodology

The methodology for this study involved a comprehensive analysis of data sourced from the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) 2022 report, which provided detailed statistics on the number and types of basic schools, the condition of these schools, the population of gifted students, and the enrolment of special needs students across Nigeria. A synopsis of the database is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Synopsis of data in UBEC's 2020 Digest of public and private schools in Nigeria

Section	Data description
Demography	School-age children at ECCDE, primary, and JSS levels by state, age, and gender.
Number of Schools	Distribution of ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by location and category.
Number of Classrooms	Availability and condition of classrooms in ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by state.
Enrolment	Enrolment for ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by state, location, class, age, and gender.
Learners Flow	Data on completion, promotion, repeaters, drop-outs, and transfers in primary and junior secondary schools by state, class, and gender.
Teaching and Non-teaching Staff	Qualifications, distribution, length of service, computer literacy, and TRCN registration of teaching and non-teaching staff in ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by state and gender.
Special Needs Education	Data on special needs children in inclusive and special needs schools, including ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by state, impairment type, and gender.
Schools Infrastructure	Availability and condition of instructional materials, furniture, facilities, and toilets in ECCDE, primary, and junior secondary schools by state.
Emergent Activities and Programmes	Data on school well-being programs, designated data officers, classes held outside, school security, curriculum implementation, agricultural education training, sports facilities, and counsellors in primary and junior secondary schools by level.

Source: 2020 UBEC Digest on public and private schools

This study focused on data related to Special Needs Education, including the number of classrooms and pupils' enrollment in both inclusive and special schools, as well as the number of teachers in special schools. The data were summarized to provide a clear overview of the current state of inclusive and special education in Nigeria. Graphs and charts were used to visualize the data, highlighting patterns, trends, and disparities. The visualised data were then interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions about the state of gifted and special education in Nigeria, with a comparative analysis against past studies and global practices to provide context. Key trends and challenges were identified, such as the preference for inclusive education and the low number of special schools, along with regional disparities in teacher availability. Based on these insights, actionable recommendations were formulated to address gaps in Nigeria's special and inclusive education system, including enhancing

resource allocation, improving teacher training, and ensuring equitable access to quality education for all students.

Results and Discussion

Number of inclusive and special basic schools in Nigeria

Figure 1 reveals a significant disparity between inclusive and special schools across the three educational levels assessed. Inclusive schools are far more numerous, with the highest number at the primary level (31,659 schools), compared to special schools, which peak at 571 at the same level. This suggests better accessibility for students with special needs within mainstream education, particularly at the primary level, but highlights a gap in specialised support, as evidenced by the low number of special schools. The data underscores the need for increased investment in special schools to ensure adequate resources for students requiring intensive support, while also emphasising the benefits of inclusive education for social integration and equal opportunities. Policymakers should consider these disparities to balance resource allocation and support both inclusive and special education effectively.

Figure 1: Number of basic schools per level and status in Nigeria

Figure 2b shows significant regional disparities in the distribution of inclusive and special schools across Nigeria. The North West consistently has the highest number of inclusive schools, particularly at the primary level with 10,875 schools, while the South-South and South East regions generally have lower numbers. This suggests a strong focus on inclusive education in the North West, possibly due to regional policies or higher demand, whereas regions like the South-South and South East may require more attention and resources to improve access to inclusive education. The differences indicate a need for targeted resource allocation to ensure equitable access across all regions. Policymakers should focus on balanced development and increased investment in regions with fewer inclusive schools to enhance the quality and availability of inclusive education, ensuring that all students have access to appropriate educational opportunities.

Overall, there are far much less special schools than inclusive schools, with the highest number at the primary level, particularly in the North West region. The geographic trend observed for inclusive schools is reflected in the special schools. The North West region consistently has the highest number of special schools, particularly at the Primary level with 181 schools, while the South South and South East regions generally have lower numbers (Figure 2b). This suggests a strong focus on specialised education in the North West compared to all other geopolitical zones.

Figure 2: Regional trend in the number of inclusive and special schools in Nigeria

a

Pupil enrolment in inclusive and special basic schools in Nigeria

Figure 3 shows pupil enrolment in Nigeria's inclusive and special schools across three basic levels: Early Childhood Care Development and Education (ECCDE), primary, and Junior Secondary Schools (JSS). The highest enrolment is found in primary inclusive schools, with 346,003 pupils, while the lowest enrolment is in JSS special schools, with 18,267 pupils. In general, inclusive schools have higher enrolment figures than special schools, with primary schools having the largest numbers at both ends of the comparison. ECCDE enrolment in inclusive schools (47,504) also exceeds that in special schools (25,782), and a similar trend is observed at the JSS level, though the enrolment gap narrows slightly (100,768 in inclusive versus 18,267 in special schools). The differences in enrolment between special and inclusive schools are in line with the differences in the number of schools in these two categories (Figure 1). These enrolment patterns suggest that more pupils with special needs are integrated into inclusive school systems, especially at the primary level, while fewer are in specialised settings, particularly at the JSS level.

These differences may have several implications for the special education sector in Nigeria. The stark contrast in enrolment between inclusive and special schools, particularly at the primary level, indicates a strong preference or policy drive towards inclusive education, potentially due to limited resources or societal efforts to integrate special needs pupils into mainstream schools. However, the significantly lower enrolment in special schools, especially at the secondary level, raises concerns about the adequacy of specialised support for pupils with more severe or specific needs. Previous studies in Nigeria and other countries with developing education sectors have highlighted challenges such as inadequate funding, trained personnel, and infrastructure in special schools, which might explain the lower enrolment figures (Eleweke and Rodda 2002; Angwaomaodoko, 2023).

While the preference for inclusive education is clear, this trend may overlook the specialised attention some pupils require, especially at the secondary level. A balanced approach, where both inclusive and special schools are adequately supported, is essential to ensure that special needs learners are not neglected.

Figure 3: Pupil enrolment in inclusive and special schools per level

Regional differences in pupil enrolment in inclusive and special basic schools

The enrolment data reveals significant regional disparities. In inclusive schools, the North West zone has the highest enrolment at the primary level with 99,845 pupils, while the South South zone has the lowest with 13,062 pupils at JSS level. The special schools, the North West zone leads in primary enrolment with 54,388 pupils, whereas the South South has the lowest enrolment at the ECCDE level with 2,693 pupils.

Historically, disparities in educational enrolment across Nigeria’s regions have been attributed to socio-economic factors, cultural attitudes towards education, and varying levels of government investment. Similar trends are observed in other countries where regional disparities in special education often reflect broader socio-economic inequalities.

To address these disparities, targeted interventions are needed to improve enrolment in underrepresented regions. This could include increasing funding, enhancing teacher training, and raising awareness about the importance of inclusive and special education. Ensuring equitable access to education for all pupils, regardless of their region, is crucial for the overall development of Nigeria’s educational sector.

Figure 4: Regional trend in pupil enrolment in inclusive and special schools in Nigeria

Pupil enrolment in inclusive basic schools based on special needs type

Figure 5 indicates that the largest category of special needs students in inclusive schools is the Gifted/talented category, comprising 39% of the total, followed by mental disabilities at 23%. The Physical and hearing-impaired categories are relatively smaller, at 10% and 9% respectively, while

Visual impairments account for 6%. The high percentage of gifted students suggests a strong emphasis on catering for advanced learners with high intellects within inclusive settings. However, the significant proportion of students with learning disabilities highlights the need for specialised instructional strategies and resources. The lower percentages for physical, hearing, and visual impairments may indicate either fewer students with these needs or potential underreporting/under-identification.

Globally, the distribution of special needs students in inclusive settings varies. For instance, in many European countries, there is a strong focus on integrating students with various disabilities into mainstream schools. The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (EASIE) reports similar trends, with a significant number of students with learning disabilities and fewer with physical or sensory impairments (EASIE, 2021). In contrast, low- and middle-income countries including Nigeria often face challenges in inclusive education due to limited resources and infrastructure (Egbedeyi and Babalola 2023).

To improve the inclusivity and effectiveness of special education, it is crucial to address the needs of all categories of special needs students. This includes enhancing teacher training, providing adequate resources, and ensuring that policies support the identification and support of all types of disabilities or special needs. By learning from global practices and adapting them to local contexts, Nigeria can better support its special needs students and ensure equitable access to quality education.

Distribution of special needs students per category in inclusive schools

(UBEC 2022)

Figure 5: Distribution of special needs learners in inclusive schools in Nigeria

Population of gifted/talented pupils/learners in inclusive schools

Because of the importance of gifted and talented learners in Nigeria development, this section assessed their recorded population about the general population of learners in basic schools. According to UBEC's data (Figure 6), there are about 47 million students at the basic level (i.e., Early Childhood Care Development and Education (ECCDE), primary and junior secondary). Out of these, 195,998 students (0.4%) are gifted and this proportion varies depending on the level, i.e., 0.8% and 0.3% at the junior secondary and primary school levels, respectively. This indicates a significant number of students who could benefit from specialised educational programs, though there may be much more, especially because there are no clear methods of identification of gifted learners in Nigeria. In developed countries, such as the United Kingdom and the United States, between 5 – 10% and 8 – 13% of the population is identified as gifted (Taber, 2007).

Figure 6: Proportion of gifted and talented learners in Nigeria's basic schools

Regional differences in the number of teachers in special needs schools in Nigeria

According to UBEC's 2022 data, there were 11,099 teachers in special schools in Nigeria's basic special needs schools with most of them(79.3%) at the primary level. The North East region had the highest number of teachers in special schools at the primary level, with 3,262 teachers. In contrast, the South East region has the lowest number of teachers at the ECCDE level, with only 112 teachers. The South West region has the highest number of teachers at the ECCDE level, with 425 teachers. These patterns suggest significant regional disparities in the availability of special education teachers. The high number of teachers in the North East at the primary level indicates a stronger focus or better resources allocated to special education in this region. Conversely, the low numbers in the South East, particularly at the ECCDE level, may indicate a lack of resources or prioritisation for early childhood special education.

Similar disparities in the distribution of special education teachers have been observed in other countries. For instance, in the United States, rural areas often face shortages of special education teachers compared to urban areas (United States Government Accountability Office – GAO 2024). In many low- and middle-income countries, the distribution of special education resources is uneven, often concentrated in more developed regions while underserved areas struggle with shortages. To address these disparities, targeted interventions are needed to ensure an equitable distribution of special education teachers across all regions. This could include policies to incentivise teachers to work in underserved areas, increased funding for teacher training programs, and improved infrastructure for special education.

Special needs student-teacher ratio

The data on student-to-teacher ratios in special schools across Nigeria reveals significant variations at different educational levels (Figure 7). The average ratios are 25 for ECCDE, 32 for primary, and 23 for JSS. The highest ratio is observed at the primary level with a maximum of 189, indicating a severe strain on teacher resources in some areas. The average values from UBEC’s data are in line with the recommended standard ratio set by the Federal Government of Nigeria (i.e., 1 teacher to 25 and 35 pupils for ECCDE and primary levels, respectively). High student-to-teacher ratios can negatively impact the quality of education, as teachers may struggle to provide individualised attention and support to each student. These patterns imply that some regions or schools may be critically understaffed,

particularly at the primary level. Historically, the pupil to teacher ratio in Nigeria, especially at the primary school level has been a significant concern. In 2010, the ratio was reported at 37.55 students per teacher, a decrease from 46.09 in 2007. This indicates a gradual improvement, although the figure remains higher than the global average of 25.28 students per teacher

For the special education segment in Nigeria, these findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions to ensure an equitable distribution of teachers. Addressing these disparities is crucial for improving the overall quality and accessibility of special education, ensuring that all students receive the attention and support they need to succeed. This could include policies to train more teachers to be deployed in underserved areas and improve infrastructure for special education.

Figure 7: Variation in the pupil to teacher ratio in special needs schools in Nigeria

Regional differences in the pupil to teachers ratio in special needs schools

The assessment of the student-to-teacher ratios in special schools across different geopolitical zones also reveals significant disparities Table 2. The highest ratios are found in the North East at the primary level (53:1) and the North West at the ECCDE level (45:1), indicating a severe strain on teacher resources in these regions. On the other hand, the lowest ratios are observed in the South South at the JSS level (11:1) and the South West at the ECCDE level (16:1), suggesting better resource allocation or fewer students requiring special education services in these zones.

Table 2: Regional difference in the pupil to teacher ratio in special needs schools in Nigeria

Region	ECCDE	PRIMARY	JSS
NORTH CENTRAL	17	17	14
NORTH EAST	26	53	40
NORTH WEST	45	38	19
SOUTH EAST	29	21	36
SOUTH SOUTH	17	14	11
SOUTH WEST	16	48	18
Total	25	32	23

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study highlighted significant disparities between inclusive and special schools in Nigeria, with inclusive schools being more numerous, especially at the primary level. The North West region has the highest number of both inclusive and special schools, while the South South and South East regions have fewer. Pupil enrolment is higher in inclusive schools, particularly at the primary level, with significant regional differences. The largest category of special needs students in inclusive schools is the Gifted category, followed by those with learning disabilities. There are also notable regional disparities

in the availability of special education teachers, with the North West having the highest number and the South East the lowest. The student-to-teacher ratios vary significantly, with some regions facing severe strains on teacher resources.

The findings indicate a strong preference or policy drive towards inclusive education in Nigeria, potentially due to limited resources or societal efforts to integrate special needs pupils into mainstream schools. However, the low number of special schools and the significant regional disparities in enrolment and teacher availability highlight the need for specialised support for students with severe or specific needs. Addressing these disparities through targeted resource allocation, increased funding, and enhanced teacher training is crucial for improving the quality and accessibility of special education in Nigeria. A balanced approach is essential to ensure that the needs of all pupils are met, promoting equity in the special education system.

To address the identified issues, it is recommended to increase investment in special schools to ensure they have the necessary infrastructure and support for students requiring intensive care. Policymakers should focus on balanced development and increased investment in regions with fewer inclusive and special schools to ensure equitable access. Enhancing teacher training and developing clear methods for identifying gifted learners are also crucial. Additionally, policies should be implemented to incentivise teachers to work in underserved areas, and awareness about the importance of inclusive and special education should be raised to improve enrolment and support across all regions. These measures aim to create a more equitable and effective educational system for all students in Nigeria.

References

- Angwaomaodoko, E. A. (2023). The Challenges and Opportunities of Inclusive Education in Nigeria. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4543299
- EASIE (2021). European Agency Statistics On Inclusive Education - 2020/2021 school year Country Report - Switzerland. https://www.european-agency.org/data/18779/datatable-country-report/2020_2021
- Egbedeyi, T.F, and Babalola A.,E. (2023). Availability and Challenges of Inclusive Lower Primary Education Schools. *Indonesian Journal of Community and Special Needs Education*. 3(2): 93-102. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijcsne.v3i2.54194>
- Eleweke, C. J., and Rodda, M. (2002). The challenge of enhancing inclusive education in developing countries. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 6(2), 113-126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110110067190>
- Taber, K. S. (2007). Science education for gifted learners? In K. S. Taber (Ed.), *Science Education for Gifted Learners* (pp. 1-14). London: Routledge

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural organisation (2020) Paper commissioned for the 2020 Global Education Monitoring Report, Inclusion and education. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373665>

United States Government Accountability Office - GAO (2024). Education Needs School-and District-Level Data to Fully Assess Resources Available to Students with Disabilities. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/gao-24-106264.pdf>